

Appendix S2. Primer pair sequences.

CHLOROPLAST PRIMERS

Forward Primers; Tag Sequence: AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACA			
	Target Name	Target-Specific Sequence (5' - 3')	Oligonucleotide Sequence for microfluidic PCR (5' - 3')
1	matK_110 F	TATATCCACTTATCTTTTCAGGAGTATATTTATGC	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATATATCCACTTATCTTTTCAGGAGTATATTTATGC
2	matK_521 F	GAAATCTTGGTTCAAACCTTCGCTA	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGAAATCTTGGTTCAAACCTTCGCTA
3	ndhF_57 F	GGAAACAGACATATCAATATGCGTGG	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGGAACAGACATATCAATATGCGTGG
4	ndhF_516 F	TGGAATGTGTTCTATCTATTAATAGGGTT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATGGAATGTGTTCTATCTATTAATAGGGTT
5	ndhF_1,022 F	TGCTTATTTTCATTTGATTACTCATGCTTATT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATGCTTATTTTCATTTGATTACTCATGCTTATT
6	ndhF_1,410 F	TTTGAAGGGCATTAAACGTTCAATT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATTTGAAGGGCATTAAACGTTCAATT
7	rbcL_106 F	ATCTTGGCAGCATCCGAGT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAATCTTGGCAGCATCCGAGT
8	rbcL_635 F	ATGCGTTGGAGAGATCGTTTCT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAATGCGTTGGAGAGATCGTTTCT
9	rpl32_79 F	AAATCTCTTTCTACTGGGAATCAAAAAG	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAAAATCTTTCTACTGGGAATCAAAAAG
10	rpoC2_91 F	ACGTTCTCTTTTCAGGCCCTTCA	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGCTTCTCTTTTCAGGCCCTTCA
11	rpoC2_524 F	GTTCCAAACGTCACCCCTCT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGTTCCAAACGTCACCCCTCT
12	rpoC2_965 F	CAAGTTGCAAATAGTTATTTACCAAGATCTG	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACACAAGTTGCAAATAGTTATTTACCAAGATCTG
13	rpoC2_1,489 F	TCAATACTAAACAAGTCCGAACATAATGAATA	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATCAATACTAAACAAGTCCGAACATAATGAATA
14	trnT_77 F	CGCATACAAATGCGATGCTCT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACACGATACAAATGCGATGCTCT
15	trnL_821 F	GGCGAAATCGGTAGACGCTA	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGGCGAAATCGGTAGACGCTA
16	trnL_1,363 F	GGGTTCAAGTCCCTCTATCCC	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGGTTCAAGTCCCTCTATCCC
Reverse Primer; Tag Sequence: TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCT			
	Target Name	Target-Specific Sequence (5' - 3')	Oligonucleotide Sequence for microfluidic PCR (5' - 3')
1	matK_715 R	AGAAGAATCCAGAAGATGTTGATCG	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAGAAGAATCCAGAAGATGTTGATCG
2	matK_1,103 R	GGAATAATTGGAACAAGGGTATCGAAC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGGAATAATTGGAACAAGGGTATCGAAC
3	ndhF_557 R	AACCTTATTAATAGATAGGAACACATTCCA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAACCTTATTAATAGATAGGAACACATTCCA
4	ndhF_1,054 R	AATAAGCATGAGTAATCAAATGAAATAAAGCA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAATAAGCATGAGTAATCAAATGAAATAAAGCA
5	ndhF_1,435 R	AAATGAACGTTTAAATGCCCTTCAA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAAATGAACGTTTAAATGCCCTTCAA
6	ndhF_2,054 R	ATCTATATAAGCAGATTATGACCAATCAT	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTATATAAGCAGATTATGACCAATCAT
7	rbcL_655 R	AGAAACGATCTCTCCAACGCAT	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAGAAACGATCTCTCCAACGCAT
8	rbcL_1,395 R	GATCTCTTTCCATACCTCACAAGC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGATCTCTTTCCATACCTCACAAGC
9	rpl32_679 R	GACACATATTTATCCAGAATATCTTCACTAAGT	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGACACATATTTATCCAGAATATCTTCACTAAGT
10	rpoC2_623 R	TGATATAACCCAGGGCTTCCA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTTGATATAACCCAGGGCTTCCA
11	rpoC2_978 R	CAGATCTTGGTAAATAACTATTTGCAACTTG	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTCAGATCTTGGTAAATAACTATTTGCAACTTG
12	rpoC2_1,520 R	TATTCAATTAGTTCCGACTTGTATTAGTATTGA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTTATTCAATTAGTTCCGACTTGTATTAGTATTGA
13	rpoC2_2,080 R	AAAGAGGATTGATTGAGTATCGAGGA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAAAGAGGATTGATTGAGTATCGAGGA
14	trnT_628 R	CGCAATTCAATATAGATTGATATAGACCC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTCGCAATTCAATATAGATTGATATAGACCC
15	trnL_1,383 R	GGGATAGAGGGACTTGAACCC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGGGATAGAGGGACTTGAACCC
16	trnL_1,786 R	ATTTGAAGTGGTGACACGAGGA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTATTTGAAGTGGTGACACGAGGA

NUCLEAR PRIMERS

Forward Primers; Tag Sequence: AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACA			
	Target Name	Target-Specific Sequence (5' - 3')	Oligonucleotide Sequence for microfluidic PCR (5' - 3')
1	ETS_F	GGATCAACAGGTAGCATTCCT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGGATCAACAGGTAGCATTCCT
2	ITS_F	GCAAAGCAGCCGGAAC	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGCAAAAGCAGCCGGAAC
3	PPR24_188F	GGTTTGAAGATGCTGTTGGTGT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGGTTTGAAGATGCTGTTGGTGT
4	PPR24_450F	TTCTTGGACCAGTATGGTATCAGC	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATCTTGGACCAGTATGGTATCAGC
5	PPR47_26F	TGTGGAAGTATGACAGATGCACG	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATGTGGAAGTATGACAGATGCACG
6	PPR62_79F	GCACGCGCTCCAGTTCTT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGCAGCGCTCCAGTTCTT
7	PPR70_665F	TCAAGGAAATGCTGGAGAAAGGAT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATCAAGGAAATGCTGGAGAAAGGAT
8	PPR123_505F	GATAAGCTCTTCTGGAGT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACAGATAAGCTCTTCTGGAGT
9	waxy_26F	TGCCATGCGATATGGAACAGT	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATGCCATGCGATATGGAACAGT
10	waxy_309F	TGGACAGTGTGCTACTGTTGAC	AACTGACGACATGGTTCTACATGGACAGTGTGCTACTGTTGAC
Reverse Primers; Tag Sequence: TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCT			
	Target Name	Target-Specific Sequence (5' - 3')	Oligonucleotide Sequence for microfluidic PCR (5' - 3')
1	ETS_R	GCATGTCGGTTCCTGCT	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGCATGTCGGTTCCTGCT
2	ITS_R	GTAATCCCGCTGACCTGG	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGTAATCCCGCTGACCTGG
3	PPR24_1008R	ACGCCCTTCTCTACTAGACC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTACGCCCTTCTCTACTAGACC
4	PPR24_565R	CATTAATCATGGTTGTCCACAGAACA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTCATTAAATCATGGTTGTCCACAGAACA
5	PPR47_811R	ATTCTGACATGATCTTGATAGCATTG	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTATTCTGACATGATCTTGATAGCATTG
6	PPR62_650R	CTCAATGTTCTCCCTTTCATCTC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTCTCAATGTTCTCCCTTTCATCTC
7	PPR70_1055R	TGCAAGAACAAGACCTTTAAGAGTAAT	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTTGAAGAACAAGACCTTTAAGAGTAAT
8	PPR123_1031R	AAGACCGTTATGTCCTTGACCTC	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTAAGACCGTTATGTCCTTGACCTC
9	waxy_446R	CAGGAGAGATCTTGTGACATGCA	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTCAGGAGAGATCTTGTGACATGCA
10	waxy_909R	GCAATTTCTCACCTTCTATACCAG	TACGGTAGCAGAGACTTGGTCTGCAATTTCTCACCTTCTATACCAG